

A comparative study of Fenton's, photo-Fenton's and other related reagents : resorcinol-TiO₂ system

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Abstract : The photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol over titanium dioxide using photo-Fenton's and other related reagents was investigated. The effect of various parameters; such as pH, concentration of resorcinol, amount of semiconductor, amount of H₂O₂, concentration of ferric ions, light intensity, effect of other ions, etc. were observed. The photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol follows pseudo-first order kinetics. A tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol using photo-Fenton's reagent.

Keywords : Photocatalytic degradation, resorcinol, titanium dioxide.

The problem of the purity of water has become one of the paramount problems faced by mankind. The self-purifying capacity of many water streams has already been exhausted, and as a consequence, many pollutants are accumulated in the circulation of water. One of the mechanism by which pollutants are degraded in nature consists of reactions of H₂O₂ initiated by solar radiations.

An important role in photochemical reactants taking place in natural waters is played by compounds of transition metals, particularly of iron¹, copper². Solar photodegradation of xenobiotic contaminants in polluted well water was also investigated³. Investigation on the mechanism of reaction between benzene and H₂O₂ in the presence of dioxygen with added Fe³⁺ or Cu²⁺ ions was made⁴.

Prousek *et al.*⁵ reported the utilization of Fenton reaction for the degradation of conventionally used dyes and coloured wastewater. Prousek and Duriskova⁶ studied the oxidative degradation of poly (ethylene glycol) by the Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions. Photo-degradation of malachite green in the presence of Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ under visible irradiation has been observed by Wu *et al.*⁷.

Recycling of waste water for electrolytic nickel plating by deionization with ion exchange resin and reverse osmosis membrane after oxidation with Fenton's reagent

was observed by Wada *et al.*⁸. Chang and Zaleiko⁹ described the utilization of photocatalytic effects of transition metals which, owing to the pronounced past irradiation effect, make possible a considerable reduction in the time of irradiation and thus an important saving of energy. Ruppert *et al.*¹⁰ studied the photo-Fenton reaction as an effective photochemical wastewater treatment process.

Lei *et al.*¹¹ studied oxidative degradation of poly vinyl alcohol by the photochemically enhanced Fenton reaction. Kinetics and quantum yield for sunlight-induced reactions via Fenton type reagents like degradation/ decolouration of concentrated solutions of orange II were studied by Bandara *et al.*¹².

Sanchez *et al.*¹³ reported the degradation of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid by *in situ* photogenerated Fenton's reagent. Gallard *et al.*¹⁴ observed the effect of pH on the oxidation rate of organic compounds by Fe^{II}/H₂O₂, whereas Walling¹⁵ studied intermediates in the reaction of Fenton type reagents.

Iron(II) is not the best donor of electron and, therefore, a search seems necessary for other related reagents, which can replace iron(II) in Fenton's reagent by some other donor ion. Therefore, the present work was undertaken.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH variation :

The effect of pH on photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol was also investigated. The results are reported in Table 1. It is evident from the data in the table that the rate of photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol increases with increase in pH upto 4.0. It was not possible to measure the reaction rate in pH range above 6.0 due to formation of some colloidal particles in the reaction mixture; making it difficult to measure the optical density.

The photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol depends strongly on the pH values of the reaction medium as the generation of OH[•] radicals is affected by the concentration of OH⁻ ions. At lower pH values than pH = 5, OH_b⁻ (OH⁻ in bulk solution) increases on the surface of semiconductor with an increase in pH. However, an increase in ArO⁻ adsorption decreases the amount of active sites. Hence, initial reaction rate is maximum near pH 4.0. On the other hand, at pH values higher than 4.0, the initial rate of reaction decreases drastically. This phenomenon can be explained on the basis of the competitive adsorption of OH⁻ and ArO⁻ on the TiO₂ surface. It is easier to replace the OH⁻ with ArO⁻ with increasing pH values due to the increasing activity of ArO⁻. The effect of pH values on photocatalytic reaction in presence of H₂O₂ may also depend upon the decomposition of H₂O₂, which is the governing step.

The decomposition of H₂O₂ is a chain reaction and it is important to know the initiation of the reaction. The initiation of H₂O₂ decomposition on an illuminated TiO₂ surface is much faster than occurring without TiO₂ (Wei

*et al.*¹⁶). A decrease in the reaction rate on increasing pH may be also due to the reaction between ferric ion and H₂O₂ regenerating ferrous ions with protons (Wei *et al.*¹⁶).

Fox¹⁷ has already pointed out that the TiO₂ surface can effectively stabilize radicals and radical ions; thus photogenerated surface associated redox intermediates may have a longer lifetime than the same intermediates generated in solution. This prolonged lifetime provides a greater chance for the reaction to occur.

The photocatalytic reaction in aqueous solution requires dissolved oxygen (Izumi *et al.*¹⁸). The Fenton type decomposition is much more pH sensitive and is applicable only in the systems with pH higher than 2.0. It appears that the photocatalytic reaction can reduce the threshold reaction time, which is defined as the point, where the slope of the reaction curve changes drastically and it indicates the initiation of major decomposition.

Effect of resorcinol concentration :

The effect of resorcinol concentration on the rate of its degradation was also observed and the results are summarized in Table 2. An adverse effect on the rate of photocatalytic degradation was observed with increasing concentrations of resorcinol.

This may be explained on the basis that resorcinol is considered as retardant for the generation of hydroxyl radicals because of its competitive adsorption on the TiO₂ surface; thus decreasing the amount of available active sites on surface of the semiconductor and, therefore, the generation of OH[•] radicals from the TiO₂ surface is a rate limiting factor for the photocatalytic oxidation of

Table 1. Effect of pH variation

[Resorcinol] = 2.72 × 10⁻³ M, TiO₂ = 0.25 g, [Fe³⁺] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, H₂O₂ = 0.20 mL h⁻¹, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm⁻²

pH	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	4.77	0.64
2.5	5.64	0.77
3.0	6.60	0.89
3.5	7.36	1.07
4.0	8.27	1.21
4.5	7.36	1.08
5.0	6.39	0.95
5.5	5.91	0.84
6.0	4.67	0.70

Table 2. Effect of resorcinol concentration

TiO₂ = 0.25 g, pH = 4.0, H₂O₂ = 0.20 mL h⁻¹, [Fe³⁺] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm⁻²

[Resorcinol] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
2.27	9.30	1.40
2.72	8.27	1.21
3.18	5.97	1.03
3.63	3.67	0.80
4.09	3.17	0.64
4.50	2.75	0.45
5.09	2.51	0.36
5.45	2.25	0.31

this type and the concentration of OH^\bullet radicals will decrease with increasing concentration of resorcinol. The oxidation rate of resorcinol can be further improved by adding more amount of H_2O_2 as the supply of OH^\bullet radicals is relatively enhanced. This was confirmed by increasing the rate of addition of H_2O_2 .

Effect of ferric ion concentration :

The effect of concentration of Fe^{3+} ion on the rate of photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol was observed by keeping all other factors identical. The range of concentration of Fe^{3+} ions in the present case was kept between $1.13\text{--}24.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. The results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of ferric ion concentration

$[\text{Fe}^{3+}] \times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$k_1 \times 10^5$ (s^{-1})	$k_2 \times 10^5$ (s^{-1})
1.13	0.90	0.10
1.50	1.09	0.14
2.25	1.75	0.25
3.00	2.35	0.41
4.50	5.11	0.82
6.00	8.27	1.21
9.00	8.05	1.16
12.00	7.87	1.00
18.00	4.70	0.60
24.00	1.64	0.21

It was observed that the rate of reaction increases on increasing the concentration of Fe^{3+} ions and it reaches a maximum value at $[\text{Fe}^{3+}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, while a reverse trend was obtained on increasing the concentration of ferric ions beyond this limit. It is known that ferric ions are reduced back to Fe^{2+} ions on exposure.

This clearly indicates that on increasing the Fe^{3+} ions in the solution, the concentration of Fe^{2+} ions also increases accompanied by the active species OH^\bullet radicals. Now this Fe^{2+} ion can generate more OH^\bullet radicals from H_2O_2 as

However, on increasing the concentration of Fe^{3+} ions further, the rate of the reaction decreases. This may be attributed to two factors (i) the increasing concentration of Fe^{3+} ions imparts a yellow color to the solution and it may act as a filter to the incident light reaching the semiconductor surface and as a consequence, the rate may decrease and (ii) the release of protons in equation (2), which causes a decrease in pH of the medium, thus; causing a retarding effect as explained earlier.

Effect of amount of semiconductor :

The amount of semiconductor is also likely to affect the rate of photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol. Different amounts of photocatalyst were used to observe this effect. The results are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of amount of semiconductor

Amount of semiconductor (g)	$k_1 \times 10^5$ (s^{-1})	$k_2 \times 10^5$ (s^{-1})
0.10	4.11	0.69
0.15	5.61	0.85
0.20	7.84	1.01
0.25	8.27	1.21
0.30	8.27	1.22
0.35	8.30	1.22

It was observed that the rate of the reaction increases on increasing the amount of TiO_2 and it reaches a maximum value for 0.25 g and then, the rate of reaction becomes virtually constant for further increase in the amount of TiO_2 .

It indicates that there is a limiting value of photocatalyst above which, the increase in the amount of photocatalyst will not affect the rate of reaction appreciably. This may be attributed to the fact that the number of exposed semiconducting particles will increase as the amount of semiconductor powder was increased and in turn, the number of electron-hole pairs will also increase. This will result into a corresponding increase in the rate of the photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol by Fenton's reagent.

As the reaction mixture was continuously stirred with a constant speed and, therefore, the number of particles exposed will remain constant even on increasing the

amount of semiconductor beyond a limit (0.25 g). On increasing the amount of semiconductor further, the number of exposed semiconducting particles will not increase as the exposed surface area will limit the number of particles directly exposed to the light source and the reaction rate remains almost constant after this limit; hence, a plateau was observed. It may also be concluded that the point of saturation depends on the geometry of the reaction vessels. This was further confirmed by using reaction vessels of different dimensions, where a downward shift was obtained for smaller vessels and an upward shift was observed in case of larger vessels.

Effect of hydrogen peroxide :

The effect of rate of addition and also the amount of H₂O₂ was also investigated on the photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol. The result is tabulated in Table 5.

Table-5. Effect of hydrogen peroxide

[Resorcinol] = 2.72 × 10⁻³ M, pH = 4.0, [Fe³⁺] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, TiO₂ = 0.25 g, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm⁻²

H ₂ O ₂ (mL h ⁻¹)	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
0.05	5.67	0.89
0.10	6.45	0.99
0.15	6.76	1.15
0.20	8.27	1.21
0.25	9.62	1.48
0.30	15.24	1.62

It was observed that as the rate of addition and consequentially amount of H₂O₂ was increased, the rate of reaction was increased and it attained an optimum value at 0.30 mL h⁻¹. The formation of hydroxyl radical is found to depend mainly on the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide and the generation of hydroxyl radicals from the TiO₂ surface becomes relatively less important.

Wei *et al.*¹⁶ have already demonstrated that there are five possible ways to initiate hydroxyl radicals in the photocatalytic reaction system with Fenton's reagent. Once the generation of hydroxyl radicals is there, a chain reaction of these hydroxyl radicals can trigger hydrogen peroxide decomposition. It has also been observed in the present investigations that the presence of both, the hydrogen peroxide and ferric ion was a requisite for the oxidation of resorcinol.

There are two important aspects pertaining to the generation of hydroxyl radicals. The number of electron-

hole pairs, which escape from the recombination, where oxygen adsorbed on the TiO₂ surface would prevent this reaction by trapping an electron and (ii) the number of hydroxyl groups present on the TiO₂ surface. In the present investigations, the step (i) seems to be more probable and it dominates the step (ii), as the pH range selected was 2.0 to 6.0. Therefore, the increase in the rate of addition of H₂O₂ will lead to a corresponding increase in the rate of the photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol with Fenton's reagent.

Effect of light intensity :

The effect of variation of light intensity on the rate of reaction was also investigated and the observations are reported in Table 6.

Table-6. Effect of light intensity

[Resorcinol] = 2.72 × 10⁻³ M, pH = 4.0, [Fe³⁺] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, H₂O₂ = 0.20 mL h⁻¹, TiO₂ = 0.25 g

Light intensity (mW cm ⁻²)	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
0.0	6.65	1.16
20.0	7.67	1.19
40.0	8.27	1.21
60.0	9.13	2.37
80.0	10.82	3.04
100.0	15.99	3.19
120.0	17.05	4.56

It was observed that the rate of reaction increases on increasing the intensity of light but a linear behavior was not observed. Since the TiO₂ powder is suspended in a stirred solution, the light intensity will affect the degree of light absorption by the TiO₂ surface there will be a corresponding increase in the rate of the photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol with increasing light intensity.

The increasing light intensity will increase the number of photons striking the TiO₂ particles per unit area per second and as a result, more electron-hole pairs are generated, which in turn, will increase the number of active species, the hydroxyl radicals.

This results in an overall increase in the rate, which can be explained by the higher amount of dissolved oxygen present in the solution, which diminishes the consumption of hydrogen peroxide (Feuerstein¹⁹). It was also observed that the slope of the plot between rate constant versus intensity of light decreases on increasing the intensity of light.

Effect of other ions :

The effect of variation of other ions on the rate of reaction was also investigated and the observations are reported in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 7. Effect of copper ion

[Resorcinol] = $2.72 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 4.0, $H_2O_2 = 0.20 \text{ mL h}^{-1}$, $TiO_2 = 0.25 \text{ g}$, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm^{-2}

[Cu ²⁺] × 10 ⁴ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)
1.2	2.00	2.92
1.4	1.88	2.75
1.6	1.76	2.54
1.8	1.57	2.27
2.0	1.32	1.90
2.2	1.20	1.68

Table 8. Effect of ceric ion concentration

[Resorcinol] = $2.72 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 4.0, $H_2O_2 = 0.20 \text{ mL h}^{-1}$, $TiO_2 = 0.25 \text{ g}$, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm^{-2}

[Ce ⁴⁺] × 10 ⁴ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ⁶ (s ⁻¹)
0.15	3.33	4.65
0.30	3.90	5.48
0.45	4.57	6.43
0.60	5.22	7.32
0.75	6.02	8.71
1.00	7.87	10.13

It has been observed that an increase in concentration of Cu²⁺ ions results in a decrease in the rate of reaction.

It has been observed that the rate of degradation of resorcinol increases with an increase in the concentration of Ce⁴⁺ ion.

The rate of reaction in presence of cupric ions decreases on increasing the concentration of Cu²⁺ ions and for ceric ion, the rate of reaction increases on increasing the concentration of Ce⁴⁺ ions. The OH[•] radicals have generally been considered to be a main oxidising intermediate for aromatic compounds in aqueous solutions (Neta and Fessenden²⁰). The transition metal ions have been used earlier to catalyse the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in order to generate hydroxyl radicals.

The catalytic effect of Cu²⁺ on the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide has been reported by Schumb *et al.*²¹, however, Walling and Goosen²² reported that the presence of various organic compounds like CH₃COOH,

CH₃COCH₃ and t-butyl alcohol affects this catalytic effect.

Fujihira *et al.*²³ observed the photocatalytic oxidation of toluene and opined that Cu²⁺ was more powerful oxidant than Fe³⁺. It may be attributed to the lower reversible redox potential of Cu²⁺ ion at semiconductor surface than Fe³⁺ ion. Ito *et al.*²⁴ reported direct conversion of benzene to hydroquinone and also proved that the substitution of Cu⁺ ion for Fe²⁺ ion in Fenton's reagent is advantageous. On the other hand, Okamoto *et al.*²⁵ observed the heterogeneous photocatalytic decomposition of phenol over titania powder. It was found that Cu²⁺ ions could be a positive or negative catalyst depending upon its concentration.

Jacob *et al.*⁴ investigated the oxidation of benzene to phenol and observed a retarding effect of the Cu²⁺ ions in Fenton's reaction. Okamoto *et al.*²⁵ suggested that this retardation in the rate of photocatalytic reaction may be due to a severe short-circuiting of Cu²⁺ ions as the Cu⁺ ion and Cu²⁺ ions form a cyclic process without generating the active intermediate and oxidising species hydroxyl radicals.

However, a reverse trend was observed in the case of cerium ions, where an increase in the rate of photocatalytic degradation was observed on increasing the concentration of ceric ions. It may be due to the fact that there is less probability of short circuiting between cerous and ceric ions contrast to the Cu²⁺-Cu⁺ ions

Mechanism :

On the basis of the experimental observations, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol with Fenton's reagent in the presence of semiconducting TiO₂ powder.

An aqueous solution of ferric ions on exposure of light dissociates water into a proton and OH[•] radical at the cost of its own reduction to ferrous ions. This ferrous ion

will decompose hydrogen peroxide into hydroxyl ion and hydroxyl radical, while ferrous ions undergo oxidation to ferric ions. TiO_2 on exposure generates an electron-hole pair as the electron from the valence band absorbs light corresponding to the band gap of TiO_2 and is promoted to the conduction band, (e^-_{CB}), leaving behind a hole in the valence band, (h^+_{VB}). This hole may dissociate the hydrogen peroxide adsorbed on the semiconductor surface into oxygen and proton.

The oxygen may accept the electron from the conduction band while hole may decompose water into a proton and a hydroxyl radical. The dimerisation of hydroxyl radicals to hydrogen peroxide may be a rate retarding step. The hydroxyl radical will degrade the resorcinol adsorbed on semiconductor surface into products. The presence of hydroxyl radicals as an active oxidising species was confirmed by the use of hydroxyl radical scavengers like 2-propanol, where the rate of reaction was drastically reduced in its presence.

A comparison :

A comparison was made of the rates of photocatalytic degradation of resorcinol with Fenton's, photo-Fenton's and other related reagents (in presence of Cu^{2+} and Ce^{4+} ions instead of Fe^{3+} ions). The order of the effectiveness of different reagents is as follows :

Although the presence of Ce^{4+} ions increase the rate of reaction on increasing its concentration, but it does not exceed the rate of reaction with Fenton's and photo-Fenton's reagent.

Conclusions :

Although a number of techniques are available for wastewater treatment but these are associated with some or other demerits. The use of Fenton's reagent for degradation of organic pollutants has also been suggested but the reaction stops after complete consumption of ferrous ions. In this context, the photo-Fenton's reagent will get an edge over Fenton's and other related reagents as ferric ions are reduced back to ferrous ions; thus making this a cyclic process. Every ferrous ion can produce many hydroxyl radicals in contrast with dark Fenton reaction, where only a single hydroxyl radical is generated with one ferrous ion. This means that the amount of ferrous salt added in dark Fenton reaction will be large to degrade the organic pollutants where as this will be small in case of photo-Fenton reaction, which is very important for any industrial use to avoid or minimise further re-

moval of the ferric or ferrous ions after the treatment of waste waters. This will increase the efficiency of the reagent for waste water treatment and, therefore, the use of photo-Fenton's reagent for this purpose will be welcome addition to the list of presently existing conventional methods of treating waste waters.

Experimental

Stock solutions of resorcinol ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) and ferric sulphate ($6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) were prepared in doubly distilled water. 27.2 mL of resorcinol was taken in a beaker and 1.0 mL of ferric sulphate solution was added to it. The total volume was made to 100.0 mL, so that the concentrations of Fe^{3+} ion and resorcinol were $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and $2.72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, respectively in reaction mixture. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 4.0 by adding H_2SO_4 and 0.25 g TiO_2 was added to it. TiO_2 was used as a semiconductor. A magnetic stirrer stirred the reaction mixture and the solution was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips, light intensity 40.0 mW cm^{-2}). The intensity of light was measured with the help of a solarimeter (Suryamapi Model CEL 201). H_2O_2 was added drop by drop intermittently at the rate of 0.20 mL per hour.

An aliquot of 2.0 mL was taken out from reaction mixture for analysis. The sample was then centrifuged because the necessary condition for correct measurement of optical density is that the solution must be free from semiconductor particles and other impurities. A centri-

Table 9. A typical run

[Resorcinol] = $2.72 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, [Fe^{3+}] = $6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, pH = 4.0, H_2O_2 = 0.20 mL h^{-1} , TiO_2 = 0.25 g, Light intensity = 40.0 mW cm^{-2}

Time (min)	Optical density (O.D.)	2 + log O.D.
0.0	0.691	1.8394
30.0	0.760	1.8808
60.0	0.695	1.8188
90.0	0.528	1.7226
120.0	0.492	1.6919
150.0	0.507	1.7050
180.0	0.481	1.6821
210.0	0.462	1.6646
240.0	0.458	1.6608
270.0	0.424	1.6273

$$k_1 = 8.27 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

$$k_2 = 1.21 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

fuge machine (Remi Model 1258) was used for this purpose. The optical density of resorcinol was determined at wavelength $\lambda_{\max} = 350$ nm by a spectrophotometer using 2.0 mL of ferric chloride (2.72×10^{-3} M). It was observed that the optical density decreases with increasing time of exposure. A plot of $2 + \log$ O.D. against time was linear and hence, it followed pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant was measured with the expression $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$. The result are summarised in Table 9.

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